

Coordination Complexes of Copper (II), Nickel (II), Cobalt (II) and Cobalt (III) with Para-substituted 1,3-diphenyltriazene

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Manuscript received 24 May 1973; accepted 9 August 1973

Bivalent metal complexes like CuL_2 , NiL_2 , NiL_2Py_2 , CoL_2Py_2 and trivalent cobalt complexes, CoL_3 , where LH = diphenyltriazene and its para-substituted chloro, methyl and methoxy derivatives, have been synthesised and characterised from magnetic, spectral and molecular weight studies. CuL_2 and NiL_2 are diamagnetic and planar; the dipyrindinates are paramagnetic and octahedral; CoL_3 are diamagnetic and octahedral. CuL_2 and NiL_2 are dimeric at high concentrations but monomeric at low concentrations which probably form 4-membered chelates.

THE complexes of copper (II), nickel (II) and palladium (II) with 1,3-diphenyltriazene (DPTH) have been shown^{1,2} to be diamagnetic with dimeric bridged structure like copper (II) acetate³. The bridging ability of the ligand has been revealed by the X-ray study⁴ of the dimeric 1,3-diphenyltriazeno copper (I) complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{DPT})]_2$. Thus, the formation of a strained 4-membered ring on chelation has been ruled out. However, NMR spectra of some metal complexes of 1,3-dimethyltriazene⁵ and monomeric behaviour of some mercury (II) complexes⁶ of 1,3-diphenyltriazene, indicate the formation of 4-membered ring chelates. Moreover, a recent X-ray structure elucidation⁷ of the cobalt (III) complex, $\text{Co}(\text{DPT})_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3$, presents a direct evidence of existence of a strained 4-membered ring in the complex.

In order to investigate further into the manner of bonding of this highly interesting ligand, a systematic study on the copper (II), nickel (II), cobalt (II) and cobalt (III) complexes with para-substituted symmetrical triazenes, has been undertaken.

The complexes prepared along with their physical properties and elemental analytical data, are recorded in Table 1. Like $\text{Cu}(\text{DPT})_2$, all the other copper (II) complexes are found to be fully diamagnetic in the solid state (Table 2), the spin-paramagnetism being completely quenched in these compounds probably due to metal-metal bond.

From the cryoscopic molecular weight measurements in benzene, the copper (II) complexes of

dichloro- and dimethyl-derivatives are found to be dimeric in concentrated solutions. However, they revert to the monomeric forms in dilute solutions (Table 3) probably forming 4-membered chelates ($\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_4 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{CuL}_2$). This tendency is not very marked with the copper (II) diphenyltriazene complex.

From the absorption or reflectance spectra, the presence of one broad highly intense asymmetric band near $16,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2) suggest the complexes to be planar because such a band is expected only from an extreme tetragonal distortion.

Of the bivalent nickel complexes of the type NiL_2Py_2 and NiL_2 (LH = a ligand molecule), the dipyrindino complexes are paramagnetic [$\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.2-3.3 \text{ B.M.}$] and those of NiL_2 types are diamagnetic (Table 2). Unlike the copper (II) complexes, the corresponding nickel (II) derivatives are highly stable in solution. The cryoscopic molecular weight measurements of these compounds in benzene also point out that the molecular weight depends on concentration. It is likely that the dimeric and diamagnetic nickel (II) derivatives, Ni_2L_4 , and the monomeric NiL_2 possess structures similar respectively, to those suggested for Cu_2L_4 and CuL_2 .

The NiL_2 compounds in solution in benzene show two absorption maxima, one strong in the region $17,500-17,800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 660-850$) and another weak at $13,300-13,600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 160-240$) (Table 2), like $\text{Ni}(\text{DPT})_2$ which was assigned square planar configuration⁸.

TABLE 1

Complex	Colour	Decomposition point (°C)	%Metal		%Nitrogen	
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
Cu(DPT) ₂ ^a	Dark green	125	13.88	13.94	18.60	18.44
Cu(DCl DPT) ₂ ^b	"	137	10.77	10.70	14.12	14.15
Cu(DM DPT) ₂ ^c	"	140	12.42	12.42	16.47	16.43
Cu(DMe DPT) ₂ ^d	"	120	11.03	11.04	14.45	14.59
Ni(DPT) ₂ .2Py	Yellowish brown	—	9.58	9.642	18.52	18.40
Ni(DCl DPT) ₂ .2Py	Yellowish green	—	7.90	7.861	15.21	15.00
Ni(DM DPT) ₂ .2Py	Yellowish brown	—	8.76	8.824	16.89	16.85
Ni(DMe DPT) ₂ .2Py	Yellowish brown	—	8.20	8.06	15.24	15.37
Ni(DPT) ₂	Brown	260	13.06	13.02	18.43	18.65
Ni(DCl DPT) ₂	Dark green	258	9.86	9.97	14.17	14.27
Ni(DM DPT) ₂	Brown	268	11.63	11.58	16.72	16.58
Ni(DMe DPT) ₂	Brown	248	10.30	10.28	14.68	14.72
Co(DPT) ₂ .2Py	Pink	—	9.69	9.685	18.37	18.40
Co(DCl DPT) ₂ .2Py	"	—	7.82	7.896	15.02	15.00
Co(DM DPT) ₂ .2Py	"	—	8.74	8.867	16.95	16.85
Co(DPT) ₃	Dark green	225	8.96	9.126	19.52	19.48
Co(DCl DPT) ₃	"	218	7.05	6.905	14.75	14.76
Co(DM DPT) ₃	"	230	8.10	8.07	17.32	17.24
Co(DMe DPT) ₃	"	202	7.08	7.13	15.21	15.24

- a. DPTH = 1,3-diphenyltriazene
 b. DCl DPTH = 4,4'-dichloro-1,3-diphenyltriazene
 c. DM DPTH = 4,4'-dimethyl-1,3-diphenyltriazene
 d. DMe DPTH = 4,4'-dimethoxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene.

TABLE 2

Complex	Magnetic susceptibility data		Spectral data		
	Temp. (°K)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar conc. in benzene	Absorption ϵ_{max} in cm^{-1}	Molar Absorbance λ_{max}
Cu(DCl DPT) ₂	301.0	Diamagnetic	5×10^{-4}	16,100	596
Cu(DM DPT) ₂	304.5	"	5×10^{-4}	15,400	872
Cu(DMe DPT) ₂	300.5	"	Solid	16,600; 14,300	—
Ni(DPT) ₂ .2Py	305.0	3.17	Solid	~23,800; ~16,100; ~11,400	—
Ni(DCl DPT) ₂ .2Py	305.0	3.32	Solid	"	—
Ni(DM DPT) ₂ .2Py	303.5	3.27	Solid	"	—
Ni(DMe DPT) ₂ .2Py	303.5	3.27	Solid	"	—
Ni(DCl DPT) ₂	304.5	Diamagnetic	1×10^{-3}	17,800; 13,600	661; 165
Ni(DM DPT) ₂	304.5	"	5×10^{-4}	17,800; 13,300	788; 182
Ni(DMe DPT) ₂	304.5	"	5×10^{-4}	17,500; 13,300	852; 242
Co(DPT) ₂ .2Py	303.0	5.08	Solid	18,200	—
Co(DCl DPT) ₂ .2Py	303.0	5.43	Solid	16,600	—
Co(DM DPT) ₂ .2Py	303.0	5.32	Solid	18,200	—
Co(DPT) ₃	304.0	0.62	2.16×10^{-4}	17,200	2000
Co(DCl DPT) ₃	296.5	0.72	3.5×10^{-4}	16,900	1537
Co(DM DPT) ₃	296.5	0.72	2.5×10^{-4}	16,900	2032
Co(DMe DPT) ₃	296.5	0.44	2.5×10^{-4}	16,000	1912

The paramagnetic nickel (II) dipyrindinates are much less soluble in organic solvents. In their reflectance spectra, three bands at $\sim 23,800$, $\sim 16,100$ and $\sim 11,400$ cm^{-1} are observed (Table 2). The low solubility of the compounds in common organic solvents, paramagnetism and spectral behaviour are suggestive of polymeric octahedral configurations, the ligands bridging the nickel (II) ions. The pyridine molecules which are likely to occupy the trans positions in the octahedra (Figure) are lost on heating giving rise to diamagnetic planar nickel (II) complexes.

With cobalt (II), dipyrindinates of similar compositions, CoL_2Py_2 , have been prepared. The pink coloured complexes are high-spin octahedral with magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) in the order of 5.0–5.4 B.M. Their reflectance spectra show a band at $\sim 18,000$

Though a dimeric cobaltous complex, $\text{Co}_2(\text{DPT})_4$ [$\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.0$ B.M.] was claimed⁸ to have been obtained from the dipyrindinate after the removal of pyridine by heating, the authors' attempt to prepare the compound under identical condition always yielded diamagnetic cobaltic complex with a metal-ligand ratio of 1:3. The compound claimed to be $\text{Co}_2(\text{DPT})_4$ might be a mixture of $\text{Co}(\text{DPT})_3$ with CoO or Co_3O_3 as the products of decomposition. Therefore, during crystallisation from benzene the inorganic moiety is removed giving rise to pure cobaltic complex.

The cobalt (III) compounds produce in benzene stable green solutions which show a strong band in the region of $16,000$ – $17,200$ cm^{-1} [$\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 1,530$ – $2,030$]. This band can be attributed to the spin-allowed transition, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ for a strong field octahedral cobaltic complex, the other spin-allowed transition, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$, being obscured by the strongly intense charge transfer band in the high energy region. The diamagnetic cobaltic complexes possibly are all octahedral and have similar strained 4-membered structures⁷.

TABLE 3—MOLECULAR WEIGHT DETERMINATION

Complex	Concentration gms./100 gms. of benzene	Freezing point Depression (°C)	Mol. weight	
			Found	Calcd.
$\text{Cu}(\text{DPT})_2$	1.71	0.10	873	
	4.21	0.23	938	456
$\text{Cu}(\text{DCI DPT})_2$	1.20	0.110	514	
	2.77	0.20	708	
	4.02	0.23	894	594
$\text{Cu}(\text{DM DPT})_2$	1.23	0.13	485	
	2.68	0.16	857	
	3.91	0.18	1113	512
$\text{Ni}(\text{DPT})_2$	2.20	0.12	937	461
$\text{Ni}(\text{DCI DPT})_2$	1.87	0.14	685	
	2.89	0.19	798	
	5.10	0.25	1046	589
$\text{Ni}(\text{DM DPT})_2$	1.27	0.11	594	
	3.24	0.19	865	
	4.12	0.22	958	507
$\text{Ni}(\text{DMe DPT})_2$	2.06	0.18	585	
	3.20	0.20	816	
	4.81	0.22	1120	571

cm^{-1} : the other band occurring near $8,330$ cm^{-1} could not be detected due to limitation of the spectrophotometer used. As in the nickel (II) analogues, the cobalt (II) dipyrindinates may have polymeric bridged octahedral configurations.

The dipyrindino cobalt (II) compound with the dimethoxy derivative could not be prepared under identical conditions as with the other three ligands, but instead a black shining crystalline compound was obtained which on recrystallisation from benzene corresponds to $\text{Co}(\text{DMe DPT})_3$, a diamagnetic cobaltic compound.

In an attempt to isolate cobalt (II) complexes, analogous to NiL_2 , from the corresponding dipyrindinates following the same procedure, invariably diamagnetic cobaltic complexes (CoL_3) are obtained.

Experimental

Preparation of the ligands :

The four ligands, 1,3-diphenyltriazene, 4,4'-dichloro-1,3-diphenyltriazene, 4,4'-dimethyl-1,3-diphenyltriazene and 4,4'-dimethoxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene were prepared according to the methods available in the literature⁹.

Preparation of the complexes :

CuL_2 : These complexes were prepared following the proposed^{10,11} methods. These are highly soluble in benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and acetone, but in solution the diphenyl and the dimethoxy compounds underwent rapid self-decomposition.

NiL_2Py_2 : The bis-pyridine complexes were prepared also according to the method of Dwyer and Mellor¹². The complexes have no definite decomposition points but begin to lose pyridine when heated above 110° and are insoluble in water, slightly soluble in methanol, ethanol, benzene, chloroform and pyridine.

NiL_2 : These compounds were prepared from the corresponding bis-pyridine complexes on refluxing in toluene for 3 hr. From the resulting solution, crystals obtained on adding petroleum-ether (b.p. 40° – 60°) were further crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum-ether. The complexes are fairly soluble in benzene, moderately in chloroform, dioxan and slightly in acetone and carbon tetrachloride.

CoL_2Py_2 : These pyridinates were prepared by following the same procedure as described for the corresponding nickel complexes. The pink coloured crystals are slightly soluble in organic solvents. The bis-pyridino complex with the dimethoxy ligand could not be prepared by this method.

CoL_3 : The complexes, CoL_3 , were obtained from the corresponding bis-pyridinates on heating at 130° – 135° for 15 hr and crystallising the products from benzene. $Co(DMe\ DPT)_3$ was obtained in an attempt to prepare the bis-pyridine complex, $Co(DMeDPT)_2 \cdot Py_2$.

$Co(DPT)_3$ and $Co(DMe\ DPT)_3$ are moderately soluble in benzene and chloroform, but $Co(DCl\ DPT)_3$ and $Co(DM\ DPT)_3$ are slightly soluble in those solvents.

Physical measurements :

The magnetic measurements of solids were made by the Gouy method with mercury tetrathiocyanato cobaltate as standard.

The absorption spectra of the complexes in solution using purified benzene as solvent and in solids using $MgCO_3$ as standard were obtained in Hilger U.V. spectrophotometer over the range 350–1000 nm ($28,570$ – $10,000\ cm^{-1}$).

The molecular weight measurements were done cryoscopically using sodium-dried redistilled benzene

(A.R.) with a Beckmann thermometer capable of giving reading upto 1/100th of a degree centigrade.

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